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**The expression of Plac8
antibody was detected using
immunohistochemistry on the
Lung Disease Spectrum Tissue
Chip (LC2083).**

customer information

Unit: Central South University for Nationalities

Personal: Qin Xuhui

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Expression of Plac8 antibody on the lung disease spectrum tissue microarray (LC2083)

Experimental Project	The immunohistochemical method was used to detect the expression of Plac8 antibodies on the lung disease spectrum tissue microarray (LC2083).
experimenter	Lian Yanling
Pathologist	He Fenling
time	Wednesday, August 1, 2018
antibody	The client provided the Plac8 antibody.
Experimental Setup	Preliminary experiment: Set three concentrations according to the antibody instructions. They are: 1:100,1:300,1:500 Experimental test sample: LC2083,1 tissue microarray for pulmonary disease spectrum Negative for the photo: LC2083, one tissue chip of pulmonary disease spectrum

Abstract :

The study employed the UltraSensitive TMS-P immunohistochemistry (IHC) method to detect the expression of the Plac8 antibody provided by the client in tissue microarrays of pulmonary disease spectra. Preliminary experiments were conducted to optimize experimental conditions, including the selection of antigen retrieval solution, retrieval method and duration, antibody incubation conditions and time, staining methodology and duration, as well as controls for the staining process.

The antibody Plac8 was provided by the client and purchased from Cell Signaling Corporation (Plac8 (E1J2Z) Rabbit mAb #13885). The ready-to-use immunohistochemical kit, UltraSensitive TMS-P Ultra-Sensitive Kit (for mouse/rabbit), was obtained from Maxsin

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Expression of Plac8 antibody on the lung disease spectrum tissue microarray (LC2083) Biotechnology Co., Ltd. (Instruction Manual No.: 40398a; Product No.: KIT-9720). The kit composition includes: Reagent A: Endogenous peroxidase inhibitor; Reagent B: Animal non-immune serum (sheep); Reagent C: Biotinylated sheep anti-mouse/rabbit IgG; Reagent D: Streptavidin-peroxidase. The DAB chromogenic system consisted of a liquid DAB enzyme substrate chromogenic kit purchased from Fuzhou Maxsin Biotechnology Co., Ltd. (Product No.: DAB-0031/1031).

The experiment included a test strip and a negative control. The negative control was processed using the same procedure as the test strip, with the primary antibody replaced by the same isotype IgG and all other conditions remaining identical.

Experiment Summary:

Negative control: No staining

Detection slide: The positively expressed region exhibits a brownish coloration, with specific, clear, and highly contrasted results as shown in the attached table.

Image reading method: Hold the label side in the left hand and review the images sequentially from left to right and top to bottom.

Pathological review results of the paraffin-embedded tissue microarray LC2083;

Position	Sex	Age	Organ	Pathology diagnosis	Grade	Staining intensity(SI)	Cellular localization	Cells type
A1	M	51	Lung	Squamous cell carcinoma	1	-		
A2	M	46	Lung	Squamous cell carcinoma	1	-		
A3	M	49	Lung	Squamous cell carcinoma	1	+++	Membranous	Tumor cells
A4	M	62	Lung	Squamous cell carcinoma	1	-		
A5	F	59	Lung	Squamous cell carcinoma	1	-		
A6	M	69	Lung	Squamous cell carcinoma	1	+	Membranous	Tumor cells

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A7	M	55	Lung	Squamous cell carcinoma with necrosis	1	-		
A8	M	57	Lung	Squamous cell carcinoma	1	-		
A9	M	46	Lung	Squamous cell carcinoma	1	+++	Membranous	Tumor cells
A10	M	65	Lung	Squamous cell carcinoma	1	-		
A11	M	68	Lung	Squamous cell carcinoma	1	+	Membranous	Tumor cells
A12	M	70	Lung	Squamous cell carcinoma	1	-		
A13	M	46	Lung	Squamous cell carcinoma	2	-		
A14	M	46	Lung	Squamous cell carcinoma with necrosis	2	+	Membranous	Tumor cells
A15	M	60	Lung	Squamous cell carcinoma	1	-		
A16	M	64	Lung	Squamous cell carcinoma	1	-		
B1	M	45	Lung	Squamous cell carcinoma	1	-		
B2	M	68	Lung	Squamous cell carcinoma	2	-		
B3	M	50	Lung	Squamous cell carcinoma	2	-		
B4	M	30	Lung	Squamous cell carcinoma	2	-		
B5	M	51	Lung	Squamous cell carcinoma	1	-		
B6	M	64	Lung	Squamous cell carcinoma	2	++	Membranous	Tumor cells
B7	F	55	Lung	Squamous cell carcinoma	2	-		
B8	M	30	Lung	Squamous cell carcinoma	2	-		
B9	M	77	Lung	Squamous cell carcinoma	3	-		
B10	M	51	Lung	Squamous cell carcinoma	3	+	Membranous	Tumor cells
B11	M	72	Lung	Squamous cell carcinoma	2	-		
B12	M	56	Lung	Squamous cell carcinoma	2	-		
B13	M	66	Lung	Squamous cell carcinoma	1	-		
B14	M	64	Lung	Squamous cell carcinoma	3	+	Membranous	Tumor cells
B15	M	65	Lung	Adenocarcinoma	1	-		
B16	M	68	Lung	Adenocarcinoma	1	-		
C1	M	64	Lung	Adenocarcinoma	3	-		
C2	M	57	Lung	Adenocarcinoma	1	-		
C3	M	75	Lung	Adenocarcinoma (tumor necrosis)	-	*		
C4	M	54	Lung	Adenocarcinoma	1	-		
C5	M	62	Lung	Adenocarcinoma	1	+	Membranous	Tumor cells
C6	F	59	Lung	Adenocarcinoma	1	-		
C7	M	60	Lung	Adenocarcinoma	1	-		

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C8	F	51	Lung	Adenocarcinoma	1	-		
C9	F	64	Lung	Adenocarcinoma	1	-		
C10	M	49	Lung	Adenocarcinoma	1	-		
C11	M	39	Lung	Adenocarcinoma	1	-		
C12	F	64	Lung	Adenocarcinoma	2	-		
C13	M	60	Lung	Adenocarcinoma	2	-		
C14	M	42	Lung	Adenocarcinoma	1	+	Membranous	Tumor cells
C15	M	66	Lung	Adenocarcinoma	2	-		
C16	M	65	Lung	Adenocarcinoma	2	-		
D1	F	46	Lung	Adenocarcinoma	3	+	Membranous	Tumor cells
D2	M	62	Lung	Adenocarcinoma	3	+	Membranous	Tumor cells
D3	M	75	Lung	Adenocarcinoma	3	-		
D4	M	39	Lung	Adenocarcinoma	3	+++	Membranous and cytoplasm	Tumor cells
D5	M	69	Lung	Adenocarcinoma	3	+	Membranous	Tumor cells
D6	F	68	Lung	Adenocarcinoma	3	-		
D7	M	44	Lung	Adenocarcinoma	2	-		
D8	F	57	Lung	Adenocarcinoma	1--2	-		
D9	M	58	Lung	Adenocarcinoma	2	-		
D10	F	64	Lung	Adenocarcinoma	2--3	-		
D11	F	53	Lung	Adenocarcinoma	2--3	-		
D12	F	46	Lung	Adenocarcinoma	3	-		
D13	M	57	Lung	Small cell carcinoma	-	-		
D14	M	49	Lung	Small cell carcinoma	-	-		
D15	M	51	Lung	Small cell carcinoma	-	-		
D16	M	66	Lung	Small cell carcinoma	-	-		
E1	M	61	Lung	Small cell carcinoma	-	-		
E2	F	31	Lung	Small cell carcinoma	-	-		
E3	F	52	Lung	Small cell carcinoma	-	-		
E4	M	60	Lung	Small cell carcinoma	-	-		
E5	M	63	Lung	Small cell carcinoma	-	-		
E6	M	28	Lung	Small cell carcinoma	-	-		
E7	F	53	Lung	Small cell carcinoma	-	-		
E8	M	46	Lung	Composite small cell carcinoma	-	++	Membranous	Tumor cells
E9	M	71	Lung	Small cell carcinoma	-	-		

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E10	F	43	Lung	Small cell carcinoma (tumor necrosis)	-	*		
E11	M	54	Lung	Small cell carcinoma	-	-		
E12	F	55	Lung	Small cell carcinoma	-	-		
E13	M	75	Lung	Small cell carcinoma	-	+++	Membranous	Tumor cells
E14	F	40	Lung	Small cell carcinoma	-	-		
E15	M	62	Lung	Small cell carcinoma	-	-		
E16	M	62	Lung	Small cell carcinoma	-	-		
F1	F	51	Lung	Small cell carcinoma	-	-		
F2	M	62	Lung	Combined small cell carcinoma and squamous cell carcinoma	-	+++	Membranous	Tumor cells
F3	M	51	Lung	Large cell carcinoma	-	-		
F4	M	58	Lung	Large cell carcinoma	-	-		
F5	F	54	Lung	Large cell carcinoma	-	+	Membranous	Tumor cells
F6	M	64	Lung	Large cell carcinoma	-	-		
F7	M	65	Lung	Large cell carcinoma with necrosis	-	-		
F8	F	61	Lung	Invasive adenocarcinoma	-	-		
F9	F	50	Lung	Invasive adenocarcinoma	-	-		
F10	F	60	Lung	Invasive adenocarcinoma	-	-		
F11	F	57	Lung	Invasive adenocarcinoma	-	-		
F12	F	60	Lung	Invasive adenocarcinoma	-	-		
F13	M	55	Lung	Invasive adenocarcinoma	-	-		
F14	F	59	Lung	Invasive adenocarcinoma	-	-		
F15	F	48	Lung	Invasive adenocarcinoma	-	-		
F16	F	63	Lung	Invasive adenocarcinoma	-	-		
G1	M	56	Lung	Invasive adenocarcinoma	-	+	Membranous	Tumor cells
G2	F	60	Lung	Invasive adenocarcinoma	-	-		
G3	M	60	Lung	Invasive adenocarcinoma	-	-		
G4	M	59	Lung	Invasive adenocarcinoma	-	+	Membranous	Tumor cells
G5	M	41	Lung	Invasive adenocarcinoma (lung tissue)	-	++	Membranous	Alveolar epithelial cells
G6	F	67	Lung	Invasive adenocarcinoma	-	-		
G7	M	51	Lung	Invasive adenocarcinoma	-	-		
G8	F	46	Lung	Invasive adenocarcinoma	-	-		
G9	M	64	Lung	Invasive adenocarcinoma	-	-		

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G10	M	62	Lung	Invasive adenocarcinoma	-	-		
G11	M	46	Lung	Invasive adenocarcinoma	-	-		
G12	F	55	Lung	Invasive adenocarcinoma	-	-		
G13	F	60	Lung	Invasive adenocarcinoma	-	-		
G14	M	71	Lung	Carcinoid	-	-		
G15	M	60	Lung	Atypical carcinoid	-	-		
G16	F	55	Lung	Atypical carcinoid	-	-		
H1	F	36	Lung	Atypical carcinoid	-	-		
H2	M	49	Lung	Atypical carcinoid	-	-		
H3	M	67	Lung	Atypical carcinoid with necrosis (sparse)	-	-		
H4	M	60	Lung	Atypical carcinoid	-	+	Membranous	Tumor cells
H5	M	65	Lung	Atypical carcinoid	-	++	Membranous	Tumor cells
H6	M	58	Lung	Atypical carcinoid	-	-		
H7	M	57	Lung	Atypical carcinoid	-	-		
H8	M	46	Lung	Carcinoma sarcomatodes	-	-		
H9	F	60	Lung	Carcinoma sarcomatodes	-	-		
H10	M	57	Lung	Carcinoma sarcomatodes (sparse)	-	+	Membranous	Tumor cells
H11	M	62	Lung	Carcinoma sarcomatodes	-	-		
H12	M	50	Lung	Carcinoma sarcomatodes	-	-		
H13	M	58	Lymph node	Metastatic squamous cell carcinoma from hilum of lung	-	-		
H14	M	62	Lymph node	Metastatic squamous cell carcinoma from hilum of lung	-	-		
H15	M	60	Lymph node	Metastatic squamous cell carcinoma from hilum of lung	-	+	Membranous	Tumor cells
H16	M	47	Lymph node	Metastatic squamous cell carcinoma from hilum of lung	-	+++	Membranous	Tumor cells
I1	M	52	Lymph node	Metastatic squamous cell carcinoma from lung (tumor necrosis)	-	*		
I2	M	61	Lymph node	Metastatic squamous cell carcinoma from hilum of lung	-	-		
I3	M	60	Lymph node	Metastatic squamous cell carcinoma from hilum of lung	-	+++	Membranous	Tumor cells

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I4	M	59	Lymph node	Metastatic squamous cell carcinoma from hilum of lung	-	-		
I5	M	58	Lymph node	Metastatic squamous cell carcinoma from hilum of lung	-	-		
I6	M	32	Lymph node	Metastatic squamous cell carcinoma with necrosis from hilum of lung (sparse)	-	+	Membranous	Tumor cells
I7	M	64	Lymph node	Metastatic squamous cell carcinoma from hilum of lung	-	-		
I8	M	77	Lymph node	Metastatic squamous cell carcinoma from hilum of lung	-	-		
I9	M	47	Lymph node	Metastatic squamous cell carcinoma from hilum of lung	-	-		
I10	M	67	Lymph node	Metastatic squamous cell carcinoma (tumor necrosis)	-	*		
I11	F	42	Lymph node	Metastatic adenocarcinoma from hilum of lung	-	-		
I12	F	48	Lymph node	Metastatic adenocarcinoma from hilum of lung	-	-		
I13	M	70	Lymph node	Metastatic adenocarcinoma from hilum of lung	-	-		
I14	M	48	Lymph node	Metastatic adenocarcinoma from hilum of lung	-	-		
I15	M	64	Lymph node	Metastatic adenocarcinoma from hilum of lung	-	-		
I16	M	65	Lymph node	Metastatic adenocarcinoma from hilum of lung	-	-		
J1	M	53	Lymph node	Metastatic adenocarcinoma from hilum of lung	-	-		
J2	F	52	Lymph node	Metastatic adenocarcinoma from hilum of lung	-	-		
J3	M	62	Lymph node	Metastatic adenocarcinoma from hilum of lung	-	-		
J4	M	31	Lymph node	Metastatic adenocarcinoma from hilum of lung	-	++	Membranous	Tumor cells
J5	M	73	Lymph node	Metastatic adenocarcinoma	-	-		

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			node	from hilum of lung				
J6	M	73	Lymph node	Metastatic adenocarcinoma from parabronchus lymph node	-	-		
J7	M	38	Lymph node	Metastatic adenocarcinoma with necrosis from parabronchus lymph node	-	-		
J8	F	72	Lymph node	Metastatic adenocarcinoma from paratracheal lymph node	-	+++	Membranous	Tumor cells
J9	F	40	Lymph node	Metastatic small cell carcinoma from hilum of lung of No.78	-	-		
J10	M	61	Lymph node	Metastatic adenocarcinoma from hilum of lung	-	++	Membranous	Tumor cells
J11	M	59	Lung	Inflammatory pseudotumor	-	+++	Membranous and cytoplasm	Inflammatory cells ,Macrophages and Alveolar epithelial cells
J12	M	67	Lung	Inflammatory pseudotumor	-	+	Membranous and cytoplasm	Inflammatory cells ,Macrophages
J13	M	30	Lung	Inflammatory pseudotumor	-	++	Membranous and cytoplasm	Macrophages and Alveolar epithelial cells
J14	F	39	Lung	Inflammatory pseudotumor	-	+++	Membranous and cytoplasm	Inflammatory cells ,Macrophages and Alveolar epithelial cells
J15	F	37	Lung	Inflammatory pseudotumor	-	+++	Membranous and cytoplasm	Inflammatory cells ,Macrophages and Alveolar epithelial cells
J16	M	60	Lung	Inflammatory pseudotumor	-	++	Membranous and cytoplasm	Inflammatory cells ,Macrophages

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Expression of Plac8 antibody on the lung disease spectrum tissue microarray (LC2083)

									ges and Alveolar epithelial cells
K1	M	67	Lung	Inflammatory pseudotumor	-	++	Membranous and cytoplasm	Inflammatory cells ,Macrophages and Alveolar epithelial cells	
K2	F	55	Lung	Inflammatory pseudotumor	-	++	Membranous and cytoplasm	Inflammatory cells ,Macrophages and Alveolar epithelial cells	
K3	M	65	Lung	Inflammatory pseudotumor	-	+++	Membranous and cytoplasm	Inflammatory cells ,Macrophages and Alveolar epithelial cells	
K4	M	48	Lung	Inflammatory pseudotumor	-	+++	Membranous and cytoplasm	Inflammatory cells ,Macrophages and Alveolar epithelial cells	
K5	M	45	Lung	Interstitial pneumonia	-	++	Membranous and cytoplasm	Macrophages and Alveolar epithelial cells	
K6	M	72	Lung	Chronic pneumonia	-	++	Membranous and cytoplasm	Macrophages and Alveolar epithelial cells	
K7	M	57	Lung	Chronic pneumonia with abscess	-	++	Membranous and cytoplasm	Inflammatory cells and Macrophages	
K8	F	70	Lung	Organized pneumonia	-	++	Cytoplasm	Macrophages	
K9	M	57	Lung	Chronic pneumonia of No.8	-	++	Membranous	Macrophages	

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							and cytoplasm	and Alveolar epithelial cells
K10	M	52	Lung	Chronic pneumonia	-	++	Membranous and cytoplasm	Inflammatory cells ,Macrophages and Alveolar epithelial cells
K11	F	61	Lung	Chronic pneumonia	-	++	Cytoplasm	Macrophages
K12	M	51	Lung	Chronic pneumonia of No.1	-	++	Membranous and cytoplasm	Macrophages and Alveolar epithelial cells
K13	M	67	Lung	Chronic pneumonia	-	++	Membranous and cytoplasm	Macrophages and Alveolar epithelial cells
K14	M	55	Lung	Chronic pneumonia	-	++	Membranous and cytoplasm	Macrophages and Alveolar epithelial cells
K15	F	46	Lung	Chronic pneumonia of No.60	-	+	Membranous and cytoplasm	Macrophages and Alveolar epithelial cells
K16	F	37	Lung	Chronic pneumonia	-	+	Membranous and cytoplasm	Macrophages and Alveolar epithelial cells
L1	M	61	Lung	Chronic interstitial pneumonia	-	++	Membranous and cytoplasm	Macrophages and Alveolar epithelial cells
L2	M	71	Lung	Chronic interstitial pneumonia	-	+	Membranous and cytoplasm	Macrophages and Alveolar

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								epithelial cells
L3	M	66	Lung	Chronic pneumonia	-	++	Membranous and cytoplasm	Macrophages and Alveolar epithelial cells
L4	M	58	Lung	Chronic pneumonia	-	++	Membranous and cytoplasm	Macrophages and Alveolar epithelial cells
L5	M	60	Lung	Chronic interstitial pneumonia	-	+	Membranous and cytoplasm	Macrophages and Alveolar epithelial cells
L6	M	68	Lung	Chronic interstitial pneumonia	-	+++	Membranous and cytoplasm	Macrophages and Alveolar epithelial cells
L7	M	69	Lung	Chronic interstitial pneumonia of No.53	-	++	Membranous and cytoplasm	Inflammatory cells and bronchial mucosal epithelial cells
L8	M	56	Lung	Chronic pneumonia	-	+	Membranous and cytoplasm	Macrophages and Alveolar epithelial cells
L9	M	62	Lung	Adjacent normal lung tissue of No.37	-	++	Membranous and cytoplasm	Bronchial mucosal epithelial cells and Macrophages
L10	M	55	Lung	Adjacent normal lung tissue of No.7	-	++	Membranous	Alveolar epithelial cells
L11	M	54	Lung	Adjacent normal lung tissue of No.36	-	++	Membranous and cytoplasm	Macrophages and Alveolar

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								epithelial cells
L12	M	72	Lung	Adjacent normal lung tissue	-	+	Membranous and cytoplasm	Macrophages and Alveolar epithelial cells
L13	M	72	Lung	Cancer adjacent lung tissue	-	++	Membranous and cytoplasm	Macrophages and Alveolar epithelial cells
L14	M	64	Lung	Adjacent normal lung tissue of No.22	-	+	Membranous and cytoplasm	Bronchial mucosal epithelial cells and Alveolar epithelial cells
L15	F	36	Lung	Adjacent normal lung tissue of No.113	-	+	Membranous	Alveolar epithelial cells
L16	M	65	Lung	Adjacent normal lung tissue	-	++	Membranous and cytoplasm	Bronchial mucosal epithelial cells and Macrophages
M1	F	57	Lung	Adjacent normal lung tissue of No.56	-	++	Membranous and cytoplasm	Bronchial mucosal epithelial cells
M2	M	68	Lung	Cancer adjacent lung tissue	-	++	Membranous and cytoplasm	Macrophages and Alveolar epithelial cells
M3	M	72	Lung	Adjacent normal lung tissue of No.27	-	++	Membranous	Alveolar epithelial cells
M4	F	42	Lung	Cancer adjacent lung tissue of No.139	-	+	Membranous and cytoplasm	Macrophages and Alveolar epithelial cells
M5	M	59	Lung	Adjacent normal lung tissue of No.155	-	+	Membranous and cytoplasm	Macrophages and

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								Alveolar epithelial cells
M6	M	46	Lung	Adjacent normal lung tissue of No.2	-	+	Membranous and cytoplasm	Macrophages and Alveolar epithelial cells
M7	M	62	Lung	Adjacent normal lung tissue	-	+	Membranous and cytoplasm	Macrophages and Alveolar epithelial cells
M8	F	66	Lung	Adjacent normal lung tissue	-	+	Membranous and cytoplasm	Macrophages and Alveolar epithelial cells
M9	M	43	Lung	Adjacent normal lung tissue	-	+++	Membranous and cytoplasm	Macrophages and Alveolar epithelial cells
M10	M	73	Lung	Adjacent normal lung tissue	-	+	Membranous and cytoplasm	Macrophages and Alveolar epithelial cells
M11	M	35	Lung	Adjacent normal lung tissue	-	++	Membranous and cytoplasm	Macrophages and Alveolar epithelial cells
M12	M	24	Lung	Adjacent normal lung tissue	-	+	Membranous and cytoplasm	Macrophages and Alveolar epithelial cells
M13	M	49	Lung	Adjacent normal lung tissue	-	++	Membranous and cytoplasm	Macrophages and Alveolar epithelial cells
M14	M	50	Lung	Adjacent normal lung tissue	-	+	Membranous and cytoplasm	Macrophages and

Expression of Plac8 antibody on the lung disease spectrum tissue microarray (LC2083)

								Alveolar epithelial cells
M15	M	55	Lung	Adjacent normal lung tissue	-	++	Membranous and cytoplasm	Macrophages and Alveolar epithelial cells
M16	M	22	Lung	Adjacent normal lung tissue	-	+	Membranous and cytoplasm	Macrophages and Alveolar epithelial cells
pheochromocytoma								

Imaging evaluation criteria: IHC assay assessment criteria: After localizing the staining results point-by-point on the microarray, the results are classified based on cell chromogenic intensity as follows: no staining indicates negative (-), light brown staining indicates weak positive (+), brown staining indicates positive (++) , and brownish staining indicates strong positive (+++); according to the proportion of positive cells: (-) refers to fewer than 10% positive cells, (+) refers to 10–25% positive cells, (++) refers to 26%–49% positive cells, and (+++) refers to over 50% positive cells. Finally, a comprehensive qualitative and semi-quantitative staining intensity assessment is derived by integrating the results, with at least 5–10 high-power fields (HPFs) randomly observed and their averages calculated.

Note: Invalid tissues or defects are indicated by * in the staining intensity column.

Experimental Methods and Materials:

- 1) 1) Bake at 60°C for 30 minutes, followed by conventional dewaxing and hydration;
- 2) 2) Antigen repair: Repair the antigen with 0.01 M citrate buffer (pH 6.0) under high pressure for 2 minutes, cool to room temperature, and wash with phosphate buffered saline (PBS) for 5 minutes × 3 times;

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- 3) 3) Close the endogenous peroxidase with 3% H₂ O₂ -methanol at room temperature for 10 minutes, then wash with PBS for 5 minutes × 3 times;
- 4) Add normal non-immune animal serum dropwise and incubate at room temperature for 10 minutes;
- 5) 5) Remove the serum, add the primary antibody Plac8 (1:300) dropwise, and incubate overnight at 4°C.
- 6) 6) Wash with 0.1% Tween-20 PBS for 5 minutes, repeated three times;
- 7) 7) Add biotin-labeled goat anti-mouse/rabbit IgG and incubate at room temperature for 10 minutes;
- 8) 8) Wash with 0.1% Tween-20 PBS for 5 minutes, repeated three times;
- 9) Add Streptomyces antibiotinolyticase-peroxidase and incubate at room temperature for 10 minutes;
- 10) 10) Maintain DAB color development for 5 minutes, then terminate the color development by washing with distilled water;
- 11) 11) Perform hematoxylin re 染色, wash with water, then thoroughly rinse and return to blue after differentiation;
- 12) 12) Routine dehydration and transparency, followed by neutral gum sealing.

Main experimental equipment and reagents

1、 Experimental Equipment

name	vender	model
tissue processor	Thermo Fisher Scientific	Excelsior AS
Tissue embedding machine	Leica	EG1150

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Tissue slicer	Leica	RM2245
Organize the barbecuing slice machine	Leica	HI1210
Constant-temperature drying oven	Chongqing Yin Hai Experimental Instrument Co., Ltd.	DGB2003
Слайд cover glass	Thermo Fisher Scientific	-
Medical microwave oven	Shanghai Zhongda Medical Application Research Institute	ZD -IIIb
Stainless steel pressure cooker	Fuzhou Maixin Biotechnology Co., Ltd.	HPC-1001
electromagnetic oven	Fuzhou Maixin Biotechnology Co., Ltd.	120-2000w
Decolorization Shaking Bed	QILINBEI ER	TS-1
turbine mixer	SCIENTIFIC INDUSTRIES, INC	G-560E
Handheld centrifuge	NATIONAL LABNET CO	C-1200
Constant-temperature digital display water tank	Changzhou Guohua Electric Appliance Co., Ltd.	HH-60
transfer liquid gun	Appendorf	-
Chemical Pen	Gene tech	-
microscope	Olympus	BX51
camera	Pixera	150CL-CU
scanner	Aperio	CS

2、 Experimental reagent

reagent	vender	Art.No	dilution ratio
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Expression of Plac8 antibody on the lung disease spectrum tissue microarray (LC2083)

absolute ethyl alcohol	Tianjin Zhiyuan Chemical Reagents Co., Ltd.		
dimethylbenzene	Tianjin Zhiyuan Chemical Reagents Co., Ltd.		
EDTA (pH 8.0) antigen restoration solution	Fuzhou Maixin Biotechnology Co., Ltd.	MVS-0098/0099 (Concentrated 50X)	1:50
CB (PH 6.0) antigen repair solution	Fuzhou Maixin Biotechnology Co., Ltd.	MVS-0100/0101 (Concentrated 100X)	1:100
PBS buffer solution	Fuzhou Maixin Biotechnology Co., Ltd.	PBS-0060/0061	
Peroxidase inhibitor	Fuzhou Maixin Biotechnology Co., Ltd.	-	
Primary antibody: Plac8	Cell Signaling	13885	1:300
Tween-20	Tianjin Tianli Chemical Reagents Co., Ltd.	-	0.5%
TritonX-100	Tianjin Dengfeng Chemicals Co., Ltd.	-	0.1%
Secondary antibody (goat anti-rabbit/mouse universal)	Fuzhou Maixin Biotechnology Co., Ltd.	KIT-9720	Use now
DAB chromogenic reagent for histochemical kits	Fuzhou Maixin Biotechnology Co., Ltd.	0031/1031	Use now
Hematoxylin stain solution	Leica	G1004	
Neutral gum	Leica	-	Use now

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Expression of Plac8 antibody on the lung disease spectrum tissue microarray (LC2083)

Appendix: Photos (magnification 200x):

Test strip; Negative control

control

Test strip; Negative

Expression of Plac8 antibody on the lung disease spectrum tissue microarray (LC2083)

Point E8: Cell membrane++ Point E8: Negative pair

Point

E8: Cell membrane++ Point E8: Negative pair

Point I3: Cell membrane+++ Point I3: Negative 对照

Point

I3: Cell membrane+++ Point I3: Negative 对照

Expression of Plac8 antibody on the lung disease spectrum tissue microarray (LC2083)

Point L1: Membrane, Slurry++ Point L1: Negative Pair

L1: Membrane, Slurry++ Point L1: Negative Pair

Point

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用免疫组化的方法检测 **Plac8** 抗体在肺疾病谱组织芯片 (**LC2083**)上的表达

客户信息

单位：中南民族大学

个人：秦绪慧

地址：

联系方式：18607186852

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Plac8 抗体在肺疾病谱组织芯片（LC2083）上的表达

实验项目	免疫组化的方法检测Plac8抗体在肺疾病谱组织芯片（LC2083）上的表达
实验者	连彦玲
病理医生	何粉玲
时间	2018年8月1日 星期三
抗体	客户提供Plac8抗体
实验设定	预实验：根据抗体说明书，设定三个浓度 分别是：1:100 1:300 1:500 实验检测片：LC2083，肺疾病谱组织芯片 1 张 阴性对照片：LC2083，肺疾病谱组织芯片 1 张

摘要：

实验采用免疫组化（IHC）的 UltraSensitive™S-P 法检测客户提供 Plac8 抗体在肺疾病谱组织芯片中的表达情况。用预实验摸索实验条件，包括抗原修复液的选择、修复方法、修复的时间，抗体孵育的条件和时间，显色的方法和时间及对显色过程的控制等。

抗体 Plac8 由客户提供，购自 Cell Signaling 公司，Plac8 (E1J2Z) Rabbit mAb #13885。即用型免疫组化即用型 UltraSensitive™S-P 超敏试剂盒（鼠/兔），购自迈新生物技术有限公司，说明书编号：40398a，产品编号：KIT-9720，试剂盒组成：试剂 A：内源性过氧化酶阻断剂；试剂 B：动物非免疫血清（羊）；试剂 C：生物素标记的羊抗鼠/兔 IgG；试剂 D：链霉菌抗生物素蛋白-过氧化酶。DAB 显色系统：液体 DAB 酶底物显色试剂盒，购自福州迈新生物技术有限公司，其产品编号为 DAB-0031/1031。

实验设检测片和阴性对照，阴性对照片与检测片操作方法相同，一抗改用同种的 IgG，其余的条件相同。

实验总结：

阴性对照：无着色

检测片：阳性表达区呈棕褐色显色，结果特异、清晰、对比鲜明，结果如附表。

阅片方式：左手持标签侧，由左至右，由上至下依次阅片

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Plac8 抗体在肺疾病谱组织芯片 (LC2083) 上的表达

石蜡组织芯片 LC2083 的病理阅片结果:

Position	Sex	Age	Organ	Pathology diagnosis	Grade	Staining intensity(SI)	Cellular localization	Cells type
A1	M	51	Lung	Squamous cell carcinoma	1	-		
A2	M	46	Lung	Squamous cell carcinoma	1	-		
A3	M	49	Lung	Squamous cell carcinoma	1	+++	Membranous	Tumor cells
A4	M	62	Lung	Squamous cell carcinoma	1	-		
A5	F	59	Lung	Squamous cell carcinoma	1	-		
A6	M	69	Lung	Squamous cell carcinoma	1	+	Membranous	Tumor cells
A7	M	55	Lung	Squamous cell carcinoma with necrosis	1	-		
A8	M	57	Lung	Squamous cell carcinoma	1	-		
A9	M	46	Lung	Squamous cell carcinoma	1	+++	Membranous	Tumor cells
A10	M	65	Lung	Squamous cell carcinoma	1	-		
A11	M	68	Lung	Squamous cell carcinoma	1	+	Membranous	Tumor cells
A12	M	70	Lung	Squamous cell carcinoma	1	-		
A13	M	46	Lung	Squamous cell carcinoma	2	-		
A14	M	46	Lung	Squamous cell carcinoma with necrosis	2	+	Membranous	Tumor cells
A15	M	60	Lung	Squamous cell carcinoma	1	-		
A16	M	64	Lung	Squamous cell carcinoma	1	-		
B1	M	45	Lung	Squamous cell carcinoma	1	-		
B2	M	68	Lung	Squamous cell carcinoma	2	-		
B3	M	50	Lung	Squamous cell carcinoma	2	-		
B4	M	30	Lung	Squamous cell carcinoma	2	-		
B5	M	51	Lung	Squamous cell carcinoma	1	-		
B6	M	64	Lung	Squamous cell carcinoma	2	++	Membranous	Tumor cells
B7	F	55	Lung	Squamous cell carcinoma	2	-		
B8	M	30	Lung	Squamous cell carcinoma	2	-		
B9	M	77	Lung	Squamous cell carcinoma	3	-		
B10	M	51	Lung	Squamous cell carcinoma	3	+	Membranous	Tumor cells
B11	M	72	Lung	Squamous cell carcinoma	2	-		
B12	M	56	Lung	Squamous cell carcinoma	2	-		
B13	M	66	Lung	Squamous cell carcinoma	1	-		
B14	M	64	Lung	Squamous cell carcinoma	3	+	Membranous	Tumor cells

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Plac8 抗体在肺疾病谱组织芯片 (LC2083) 上的表达

B15	M	65	Lung	Adenocarcinoma	1	-		
B16	M	68	Lung	Adenocarcinoma	1	-		
C1	M	64	Lung	Adenocarcinoma	3	-		
C2	M	57	Lung	Adenocarcinoma	1	-		
C3	M	75	Lung	Adenocarcinoma (tumor necrosis)	-	*		
C4	M	54	Lung	Adenocarcinoma	1	-		
C5	M	62	Lung	Adenocarcinoma	1	+	Membranous	Tumor cells
C6	F	59	Lung	Adenocarcinoma	1	-		
C7	M	60	Lung	Adenocarcinoma	1	-		
C8	F	51	Lung	Adenocarcinoma	1	-		
C9	F	64	Lung	Adenocarcinoma	1	-		
C10	M	49	Lung	Adenocarcinoma	1	-		
C11	M	39	Lung	Adenocarcinoma	1	-		
C12	F	64	Lung	Adenocarcinoma	2	-		
C13	M	60	Lung	Adenocarcinoma	2	-		
C14	M	42	Lung	Adenocarcinoma	1	+	Membranous	Tumor cells
C15	M	66	Lung	Adenocarcinoma	2	-		
C16	M	65	Lung	Adenocarcinoma	2	-		
D1	F	46	Lung	Adenocarcinoma	3	+	Membranous	Tumor cells
D2	M	62	Lung	Adenocarcinoma	3	+	Membranous	Tumor cells
D3	M	75	Lung	Adenocarcinoma	3	-		
D4	M	39	Lung	Adenocarcinoma	3	+++	Membranous and cytoplasm	Tumor cells
D5	M	69	Lung	Adenocarcinoma	3	+	Membranous	Tumor cells
D6	F	68	Lung	Adenocarcinoma	3	-		
D7	M	44	Lung	Adenocarcinoma	2	-		
D8	F	57	Lung	Adenocarcinoma	1--2	-		
D9	M	58	Lung	Adenocarcinoma	2	-		
D10	F	64	Lung	Adenocarcinoma	2--3	-		
D11	F	53	Lung	Adenocarcinoma	2--3	-		
D12	F	46	Lung	Adenocarcinoma	3	-		
D13	M	57	Lung	Small cell carcinoma	-	-		
D14	M	49	Lung	Small cell carcinoma	-	-		
D15	M	51	Lung	Small cell carcinoma	-	-		
D16	M	66	Lung	Small cell carcinoma	-	-		
E1	M	61	Lung	Small cell carcinoma	-	-		

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Plac8 抗体在肺疾病谱组织芯片 (LC2083) 上的表达

E2	F	31	Lung	Small cell carcinoma	-	-		
E3	F	52	Lung	Small cell carcinoma	-	-		
E4	M	60	Lung	Small cell carcinoma	-	-		
E5	M	63	Lung	Small cell carcinoma	-	-		
E6	M	28	Lung	Small cell carcinoma	-	-		
E7	F	53	Lung	Small cell carcinoma	-	-		
E8	M	46	Lung	Composite small cell carcinoma	-	++	Membranous	Tumor cells
E9	M	71	Lung	Small cell carcinoma	-	-		
E10	F	43	Lung	Small cell carcinoma (tumor necrosis)	-	*		
E11	M	54	Lung	Small cell carcinoma	-	-		
E12	F	55	Lung	Small cell carcinoma	-	-		
E13	M	75	Lung	Small cell carcinoma	-	+++	Membranous	Tumor cells
E14	F	40	Lung	Small cell carcinoma	-	-		
E15	M	62	Lung	Small cell carcinoma	-	-		
E16	M	62	Lung	Small cell carcinoma	-	-		
F1	F	51	Lung	Small cell carcinoma	-	-		
F2	M	62	Lung	Combined small cell carcinoma and squamous cell carcinoma	-	+++	Membranous	Tumor cells
F3	M	51	Lung	Large cell carcinoma	-	-		
F4	M	58	Lung	Large cell carcinoma	-	-		
F5	F	54	Lung	Large cell carcinoma	-	+	Membranous	Tumor cells
F6	M	64	Lung	Large cell carcinoma	-	-		
F7	M	65	Lung	Large cell carcinoma with necrosis	-	-		
F8	F	61	Lung	Invasive adenocarcinoma	-	-		
F9	F	50	Lung	Invasive adenocarcinoma	-	-		
F10	F	60	Lung	Invasive adenocarcinoma	-	-		
F11	F	57	Lung	Invasive adenocarcinoma	-	-		
F12	F	60	Lung	Invasive adenocarcinoma	-	-		
F13	M	55	Lung	Invasive adenocarcinoma	-	-		
F14	F	59	Lung	Invasive adenocarcinoma	-	-		
F15	F	48	Lung	Invasive adenocarcinoma	-	-		
F16	F	63	Lung	Invasive adenocarcinoma	-	-		
G1	M	56	Lung	Invasive adenocarcinoma	-	+	Membranous	Tumor cells
G2	F	60	Lung	Invasive adenocarcinoma	-	-		
G3	M	60	Lung	Invasive adenocarcinoma	-	-		
G4	M	59	Lung	Invasive adenocarcinoma	-	+	Membranous	Tumor cells

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Plac8 抗体在肺疾病谱组织芯片 (LC2083) 上的表达

G5	M	41	Lung	Invasive adenocarcinoma (lung tissue)	-	++	Membranous	Alveolar epithelial cells
G6	F	67	Lung	Invasive adenocarcinoma	-	-		
G7	M	51	Lung	Invasive adenocarcinoma	-	-		
G8	F	46	Lung	Invasive adenocarcinoma	-	-		
G9	M	64	Lung	Invasive adenocarcinoma	-	-		
G10	M	62	Lung	Invasive adenocarcinoma	-	-		
G11	M	46	Lung	Invasive adenocarcinoma	-	-		
G12	F	55	Lung	Invasive adenocarcinoma	-	-		
G13	F	60	Lung	Invasive adenocarcinoma	-	-		
G14	M	71	Lung	Carcinoid	-	-		
G15	M	60	Lung	Atypical carcinoid	-	-		
G16	F	55	Lung	Atypical carcinoid	-	-		
H1	F	36	Lung	Atypical carcinoid	-	-		
H2	M	49	Lung	Atypical carcinoid	-	-		
H3	M	67	Lung	Atypical carcinoid with necrosis (sparse)	-	-		
H4	M	60	Lung	Atypical carcinoid	-	+	Membranous	Tumor cells
H5	M	65	Lung	Atypical carcinoid	-	++	Membranous	Tumor cells
H6	M	58	Lung	Atypical carcinoid	-	-		
H7	M	57	Lung	Atypical carcinoid	-	-		
H8	M	46	Lung	Carcinoma sarcomatodes	-	-		
H9	F	60	Lung	Carcinoma sarcomatodes	-	-		
H10	M	57	Lung	Carcinoma sarcomatodes (sparse)	-	+	Membranous	Tumor cells
H11	M	62	Lung	Carcinoma sarcomatodes	-	-		
H12	M	50	Lung	Carcinoma sarcomatodes	-	-		
H13	M	58	Lymph node	Metastatic squamous cell carcinoma from hilum of lung	-	-		
H14	M	62	Lymph node	Metastatic squamous cell carcinoma from hilum of lung	-	-		
H15	M	60	Lymph node	Metastatic squamous cell carcinoma from hilum of lung	-	+	Membranous	Tumor cells
H16	M	47	Lymph node	Metastatic squamous cell carcinoma from hilum of lung	-	+++	Membranous	Tumor cells
I1	M	52	Lymph node	Metastatic squamous cell carcinoma from lung (tumor necrosis)	-	*		

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Plac8 抗体在肺疾病谱组织芯片 (LC2083) 上的表达

I2	M	61	Lymph node	Metastatic squamous cell carcinoma from hilum of lung	-	-		
I3	M	60	Lymph node	Metastatic squamous cell carcinoma from hilum of lung	-	+++	Membranous	Tumor cells
I4	M	59	Lymph node	Metastatic squamous cell carcinoma from hilum of lung	-	-		
I5	M	58	Lymph node	Metastatic squamous cell carcinoma from hilum of lung	-	-		
I6	M	32	Lymph node	Metastatic squamous cell carcinoma with necrosis from hilum of lung (sparse)	-	+	Membranous	Tumor cells
I7	M	64	Lymph node	Metastatic squamous cell carcinoma from hilum of lung	-	-		
I8	M	77	Lymph node	Metastatic squamous cell carcinoma from hilum of lung	-	-		
I9	M	47	Lymph node	Metastatic squamous cell carcinoma from hilum of lung	-	-		
I10	M	67	Lymph node	Metastatic squamous cell carcinoma (tumor necrosis)	-	*		
I11	F	42	Lymph node	Metastatic adenocarcinoma from hilum of lung	-	-		
I12	F	48	Lymph node	Metastatic adenocarcinoma from hilum of lung	-	-		
I13	M	70	Lymph node	Metastatic adenocarcinoma from hilum of lung	-	-		
I14	M	48	Lymph node	Metastatic adenocarcinoma from hilum of lung	-	-		
I15	M	64	Lymph node	Metastatic adenocarcinoma from hilum of lung	-	-		
I16	M	65	Lymph node	Metastatic adenocarcinoma from hilum of lung	-	-		
J1	M	53	Lymph node	Metastatic adenocarcinoma from hilum of lung	-	-		
J2	F	52	Lymph node	Metastatic adenocarcinoma from hilum of lung	-	-		
J3	M	62	Lymph node	Metastatic adenocarcinoma from hilum of lung	-	-		
J4	M	31	Lymph node	Metastatic adenocarcinoma	-	++	Membranous	Tumor cells

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Plac8 抗体在肺疾病谱组织芯片 (LC2083) 上的表达

			node	from hilum of lung				
J5	M	73	Lymph node	Metastatic adenocarcinoma from hilum of lung	-	-		
J6	M	73	Lymph node	Metastatic adenocarcinoma from parabronchus lymph node	-	-		
J7	M	38	Lymph node	Metastatic adenocarcinoma with necrosis from parabronchus lymph node	-	-		
J8	F	72	Lymph node	Metastatic adenocarcinoma from paratracheal lymph node	-	+++	Membranous	Tumor cells
J9	F	40	Lymph node	Metastatic small cell carcinoma from hilum of lung of No.78	-	-		
J10	M	61	Lymph node	Metastatic adenocarcinoma from hilum of lung	-	++	Membranous	Tumor cells
J11	M	59	Lung	Inflammatory pseudotumor	-	+++	Membranous and cytoplasm	Inflammatory cells ,Macrophages and Alveolar epithelial cells
J12	M	67	Lung	Inflammatory pseudotumor	-	+	Membranous and cytoplasm	Inflammatory cells ,Macrophages
J13	M	30	Lung	Inflammatory pseudotumor	-	++	Membranous and cytoplasm	Macrophages and Alveolar epithelial cells
J14	F	39	Lung	Inflammatory pseudotumor	-	+++	Membranous and cytoplasm	Inflammatory cells ,Macrophages and Alveolar epithelial cells
J15	F	37	Lung	Inflammatory pseudotumor	-	+++	Membranous and cytoplasm	Inflammatory cells ,Macrophages and Alveolar epithelial cells
J16	M	60	Lung	Inflammatory pseudotumor	-	++	Membranous and cytoplasm	Inflammatory cells ,Macrophages and

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Plac8 抗体在肺疾病谱组织芯片 (LC2083) 上的表达

								Alveolar epithelial cells
K1	M	67	Lung	Inflammatory pseudotumor	-	++	Membranous and cytoplasm	Inflammatory cells ,Macrophages and Alveolar epithelial cells
K2	F	55	Lung	Inflammatory pseudotumor	-	++	Membranous and cytoplasm	Inflammatory cells ,Macrophages and Alveolar epithelial cells
K3	M	65	Lung	Inflammatory pseudotumor	-	+++	Membranous and cytoplasm	Inflammatory cells ,Macrophages and Alveolar epithelial cells
K4	M	48	Lung	Inflammatory pseudotumor	-	+++	Membranous and cytoplasm	Inflammatory cells ,Macrophages and Alveolar epithelial cells
K5	M	45	Lung	Interstitial pneumonia	-	++	Membranous and cytoplasm	Macrophages and Alveolar epithelial cells
K6	M	72	Lung	Chronic pneumonia	-	++	Membranous and cytoplasm	Macrophages and Alveolar epithelial cells
K7	M	57	Lung	Chronic pneumonia with abscess	-	++	Membranous and cytoplasm	Inflammatory cells and Macrophages
K8	F	70	Lung	Organized pneumonia	-	++	Cytoplasm	Macrophages
K9	M	57	Lung	Chronic pneumonia of No.8	-	++	Membranous and cytoplasm	Macrophages and Alveolar epithelial cells
K10	M	52	Lung	Chronic pneumonia	-	++	Membranous	Inflammatory

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Plac8 抗体在肺疾病谱组织芯片 (LC2083) 上的表达

							and cytoplasm	cells ,Macrop hages and Alveolar epithelial cells
K11	F	61	Lung	Chronic pneumonia	-	++	Cytoplasm	Macrophages
K12	M	51	Lung	Chronic pneumonia of No.1	-	++	Membranous and cytoplasm	Macrophages and Alveolar epithelial cells
K13	M	67	Lung	Chronic pneumonia	-	++	Membranous and cytoplasm	Macrophages and Alveolar epithelial cells
K14	M	55	Lung	Chronic pneumonia	-	++	Membranous and cytoplasm	Macrophages and Alveolar epithelial cells
K15	F	46	Lung	Chronic pneumonia of No.60	-	+	Membranous and cytoplasm	Macrophages and Alveolar epithelial cells
K16	F	37	Lung	Chronic pneumonia	-	+	Membranous and cytoplasm	Macrophages and Alveolar epithelial cells
L1	M	61	Lung	Chronic interstitial pneumonia	-	++	Membranous and cytoplasm	Macrophages and Alveolar epithelial cells
L2	M	71	Lung	Chronic interstitial pneumonia	-	+	Membranous and cytoplasm	Macrophages and Alveolar epithelial cells
L3	M	66	Lung	Chronic pneumonia	-	++	Membranous and cytoplasm	Macrophages and Alveolar epithelial cells
L4	M	58	Lung	Chronic pneumonia	-	++	Membranous and	Macrophages and

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Plac8 抗体在肺疾病谱组织芯片 (LC2083) 上的表达

							cytoplasm	Alveolar epithelial cells
L5	M	60	Lung	Chronic interstitial pneumonia	-	+	Membranous and cytoplasm	Macrophages and Alveolar epithelial cells
L6	M	68	Lung	Chronic interstitial pneumonia	-	+++	Membranous and cytoplasm	Macrophages and Alveolar epithelial cells
L7	M	69	Lung	Chronic interstitial pneumonia of No.53	-	++	Membranous and cytoplasm	Inflammatory cells and bronchial mucosal epithelial cells
L8	M	56	Lung	Chronic pneumonia	-	+	Membranous and cytoplasm	Macrophages and Alveolar epithelial cells
L9	M	62	Lung	Adjacent normal lung tissue of No.37	-	++	Membranous and cytoplasm	Bronchial mucosal epithelial cells and Macrophages
L10	M	55	Lung	Adjacent normal lung tissue of No.7	-	++	Membranous	Alveolar epithelial cells
L11	M	54	Lung	Adjacent normal lung tissue of No.36	-	++	Membranous and cytoplasm	Macrophages and Alveolar epithelial cells
L12	M	72	Lung	Adjacent normal lung tissue	-	+	Membranous and cytoplasm	Macrophages and Alveolar epithelial cells
L13	M	72	Lung	Cancer adjacent lung tissue	-	++	Membranous and cytoplasm	Macrophages and Alveolar epithelial cells
L14	M	64	Lung	Adjacent normal lung tissue of	-	+	Membranous	Bronchial

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Plac8 抗体在肺疾病谱组织芯片 (LC2083) 上的表达

				No.22			and cytoplasm	mucosal epithelial cells and Alveolar epithelial cells
L15	F	36	Lung	Adjacent normal lung tissue of No.113	-	+	Membranous	Alveolar epithelial cells
L16	M	65	Lung	Adjacent normal lung tissue	-	++	Membranous and cytoplasm	Bronchial mucosal epithelial cells and Macrophages
M1	F	57	Lung	Adjacent normal lung tissue of No.56	-	++	Membranous and cytoplasm	Bronchial mucosal epithelial cells
M2	M	68	Lung	Cancer adjacent lung tissue	-	++	Membranous and cytoplasm	Macrophages and Alveolar epithelial cells
M3	M	72	Lung	Adjacent normal lung tissue of No.27	-	++	Membranous	Alveolar epithelial cells
M4	F	42	Lung	Cancer adjacent lung tissue of No.139	-	+	Membranous and cytoplasm	Macrophages and Alveolar epithelial cells
M5	M	59	Lung	Adjacent normal lung tissue of No.155	-	+	Membranous and cytoplasm	Macrophages and Alveolar epithelial cells
M6	M	46	Lung	Adjacent normal lung tissue of No.2	-	+	Membranous and cytoplasm	Macrophages and Alveolar epithelial cells
M7	M	62	Lung	Adjacent normal lung tissue	-	+	Membranous and cytoplasm	Macrophages and Alveolar epithelial cells
M8	F	66	Lung	Adjacent normal lung tissue	-	+	Membranous and cytoplasm	Macrophages and Alveolar

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								epithelial cells
M9	M	43	Lung	Adjacent normal lung tissue	-	+++	Membranous and cytoplasm	Macrophages and Alveolar epithelial cells
M10	M	73	Lung	Adjacent normal lung tissue	-	+	Membranous and cytoplasm	Macrophages and Alveolar epithelial cells
M11	M	35	Lung	Adjacent normal lung tissue	-	++	Membranous and cytoplasm	Macrophages and Alveolar epithelial cells
M12	M	24	Lung	Adjacent normal lung tissue	-	+	Membranous and cytoplasm	Macrophages and Alveolar epithelial cells
M13	M	49	Lung	Adjacent normal lung tissue	-	++	Membranous and cytoplasm	Macrophages and Alveolar epithelial cells
M14	M	50	Lung	Adjacent normal lung tissue	-	+	Membranous and cytoplasm	Macrophages and Alveolar epithelial cells
M15	M	55	Lung	Adjacent normal lung tissue	-	++	Membranous and cytoplasm	Macrophages and Alveolar epithelial cells
M16	M	22	Lung	Adjacent normal lung tissue	-	+	Membranous and cytoplasm	Macrophages and Alveolar epithelial cells
pheochromocytoma								

阅片标准: IHC 实验评判标准: 对芯片上逐点染色结果进行定位后根据细胞显色强度判为: 不着色为阴性 (-)、着浅棕色为弱阳性 (+), 着棕色为阳性 (++) , 着棕褐色为强阳性 (+++); 依照阳性细

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胞数量可分为: (-)指阳性细胞小于 10%, (+)指阳性细胞数在 10-25%, (++)指阳性细胞数在 26%-49% 之间, (+++) 指阳性细胞数在 50%以上。最后根据两者的结果进行综合评判得出定性半定量的着色强度结果, 至少随机观察 5-10 个 HPF, 取其均值。

注: 无效组织或缺点在着色强度栏内用*表示

实验方法和材料:

- 1) 60℃烤片 30 分钟, 常规脱蜡水化;
- 2) 抗原修复: 以 0.01M 柠檬酸缓冲液 (pH6.0)高压 2 分钟修复抗原, 冷却至室温, 磷酸盐缓冲液 (PBS) 洗 5 分钟×3 次;
- 3) 用 3% H_2O_2 -甲醇封闭内源性过氧化物酶, 室温 10 分钟, PBS 洗 5 分钟×3 次;
- 4) 滴加正常非免疫动物血清, 室温 10 分钟;
- 5) 除去血清, 滴加一抗 Plac8 (1:300), 4℃ 冰箱过夜;
- 6) 用 0.1%Tween-20 PBS 洗 5 分钟×3 次;
- 7) 滴加生物素标记的羊抗鼠/兔 IgG, 室温孵育 10 分钟;
- 8) 用 0.1%Tween-20 PBS 洗 5 分钟×3 次;
- 9) 滴加链霉菌抗生物素蛋白-过氧化物酶, 室温孵育 10 分钟;
- 10) DAB 显色 5 分钟, 蒸馏水洗终止显色;
- 11) 苏木素复染、水洗、分化后充分水洗返蓝;
- 12) 常规脱水透明, 中性树胶封片。

主要实验器材及试剂

1、实验器材

名称	厂家	型号
组织脱水机	Thermo Fisher Scientific	Excelsior AS
组织包埋机	Leica	EG1150
组织切片机	Leica	RM2245

西安艾丽娜生物科技有限公司

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组织摊烤片机	Leica	HI1210
恒温干燥箱	重庆银河试验仪器有限公司	DGB2003
载玻片	Thermo Fisher Scientific	-
盖玻片	Fisherbrand	-
医用微波炉	上海中达医学应用研究所	ZD -IIIb
不锈钢压力锅	福州迈新生物科技有限公司	HPC-1001
电磁炉	福州迈新生物科技有限公司	120-2000w
脱色摇床	QILINBEI ER	TS-1
涡旋混合器	SCIENTIFIC INDUSTRIES, INC	G-560E
掌上离心机	NATIONAL LABNET CO	C-1200
恒温数显水箱	常州国华电器有限公司	HH-60
移液枪	Appendorf	-
组化笔	Gene tech	-
显微镜	Olympus	BX51
照相机	Pixera	150CL-CU
扫描仪	Aperio	CS

2、实验试剂

试剂	厂家	货号	稀释比
无水乙醇	天津致远化学试剂有限公司		
二甲苯	天津致远化学试剂有限公司		
EDTA (PH8.0) 抗原修复液	福州迈新生物科技有限公司	MVS-0098/0099 (浓缩型 50X)	1:50
CB(PH6.0) 抗原修复液	福州迈新生物科技有限公司	MVS-0100/0101 (浓缩型 100X)	1:100
PBS 缓冲液	福州迈新生物科技有限公司	PBS-0060/0061	
过氧化物酶阻断剂	福州迈新生物科技有限公司	-	
一抗: Plac8	Cell Signaling	13885	1:300

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Tween-20	天津市天力化学试剂有限公司	-	0.5%
TritonX-100	天津登丰化学品有限公司	-	0.1%
二抗 (山羊抗兔鼠通用)	福州迈新生物科技有限公司	KIT-9720	即用
组化试剂盒 DAB 显色剂	福州迈新生物科技有限公司	0031/1031	即用
苏木素染液	Leica	G1004	
中性树胶	Leica	-	即用

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附：照片（放大倍数 200x）：
检测片

阴性对照

第 E8 点 胞膜++

第 E8 点 阴对

第 I3 点 胞膜+++

第 I3 点 阴对

第 L1 点 膜、浆++

第 L1 点 阴对